

THE LINGUISTIC STUDY OF OFFICIAL DOCUMENTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: In modern linguistics in recent years, become a common trend in the study of applied linguistics. Texts of documents of international organizations belong to the official style of language and have common linguistic characteristics. In the XXIst century, when globalization is highly developed, official style of different languages have most common in their content. Thus, the language of the legal documents of the new Europe of the 21st century, based on the Euro English, considerably differs from the language of the international organizations in the 70-80s of the last century. The article into pragmatic, structural and linguistic peculiarities of the texts of the Council of Europe official documents will help understand their role in diplomatic communication, which is important for successful comprehension and translation of the texts of this category.

Keywords: pragmatics, structure, communication, legal documents, functional stylistics, styles, document, text, logicity, accuracy, meaning and so on.

In modern linguistics in recent years, become a common trend in the study of applied linguistics. Texts of documents of international organizations belong to the official style of language and have common linguistic characteristics. In the XXI century, when globalization is highly developed, official style of different languages has most common in their content.

Thus, the language of the legal documents of the new Europe of the 21st century, based on the Euro English, considerably differs from the language of the international organizations in the 70-80s of the last century.

Representatives of the not less well-known Prague school -V.Mathesius, T.Vachek, J.Havranek and others focused their attention on the priority of the situational appropriateness in the choice of language varieties for their adequate functioning.

Thus, *functional stylistics*, which became and remains an international, very important trend in style study, deals with sets, "paradigms" of language

units of all levels of language hierarchy serving to accommodate the needs of certain typified communicative situations. These paradigms are known as **functional styles** of the language.¹

Functional style is a system of interrelated language means serving a definite aim in communication. It is the coordination of the language means and stylistic devices which shapes the distinctive features of each style and not the language means or stylistic devices themselves.

The English literary system has evolved a number of styles easily distinguishable one from another. They are not homogenous and fall into several variants of having some central point of resemblance or better to say. All integrated by the invariant – the abstract ideal system.

They are:

1. **official style**, represented in all kinds of official documents and papers;
2. **scientific style**, found in articles, brochures, monographs and other scientific and academic publications;
3. **publicist style**, covering such genres as essay, feature article, most writings of "new journalism", public speeches, etc.;
4. **newspaper style**, observed in the majority of information materials printed in newspapers;
5. **belles-lettres style**, embracing numerous and versatile genres of imaginative writing.

A document (noun from latin "**documentum**" – lesson, instruction, warning), is a bounded physical or digital representation of a body of information designed with the capacity (and usually intent) to communicate. A document may manifest symbolic, diagrammatic or sensory-representational information.²

Peculiar features of the style of official documents in English are:

- its substantiveness

¹ Гальперин И.Р. Стилистика английского языка

² Арнольд И.В. Лексикология современного английского языка. – М.: Просвещение, 1966. – 364 с.

- logicity (strict consistency, clear connection between main idea and details)
- accuracy
- objectivity
- subsequent lucidity
- clarity.

All texts of this type tend to use the language means that contribute to satisfaction of needs of this communication sphere. The translation of official documents is a subfield of specialized legal translation. It requires absolute precision and the exclusive use of professional terms approved by the relevant official bodies.

1. On the vocabulary level translation of official documents, first of all, implies use of special terminology. Terms must provide clear and accurate definition of real objects and phenomena; establish unambiguous comprehension of transmitted information by specialists.

2. Uppermost, in translation the term must be precise, i.e. it must have strictly determined meaning which can be developed by means of logical definition that removes the place of defined concept in the paradigm of this certain field. For the same reason the term must be monosemantic and, in this regard, context-14 independent. In other words, it must have its own precise meaning which is determined by its definition in all its occurrences in any text, thus, person who uses the term doesn't have to clarify its meaning in different contexts.

3. Term precision is directly connected with the demand that every notion should have only one corresponding term, i.e. not to have synonymic terms with corresponding meanings. A term should be the part of strict logical system. Terms meanings and their definitions should conform to the rules of logical classification which clearly distinguishes between objects and notions and doesn't allow ambiguity or contradictoriness.

4. Besides, any term must have strictly objective definition with no secondary meaning which detracts specialist's attention adding the element of **subjectivity**.

Official documents are written in a formal, "cold" or matter-of-fact style of speech. The style of official documents or 'officialese' as it is sometimes called, is not homogeneous.

The peculiar features common for all stylistic varieties of official documents are the following:

- the use of abbreviations, conventional symbols and contractions;
- the use of words in their logical dictionary meaning;
- absence of emotiveness;
- general syntactical mode of combining several pronouncement into one sentence.

The lexicon of the standard documents consists of common words and great many of the special terms, which cannot be found out in the ordinary dictionary. One part of common words is known for the pupil from school or other original course of the English language.

There are some peculiarities of translation of some standard documents. Notwithstanding the seeming simplicity the translation of birth certificate or marriage certificate is no such a simple task. Too many special terms (names of institutions, positions), which cannot be found out in the ordinary dictionary, are used in these documents. That's why only the translator with wide experience of translation of such documents can translate them.

The big problem is that some standard documents must be apostilled or have notary certification what can be done only if the translation is done by the professional translator.

For example, the peculiarity of notary certification of passport translation consists in the fact that the notary doesn't certify a copy of passport and only confirms the translation authenticity.

Other part of common words is unknown by the pupil and represents that basic lexical reserve, which they should acquire in learning process. This part of common words can conditionally be subdivided on some groups:

Words, which on the first stage of tutoring usually are not studied. *E. g. to regard – hisoblamoq, ko`rib chiqmoq, e`tiborga olmoq.*

Words used in meanings, distinct from what pupils have acquired in original course. Here it is necessary to refer a great many of auxiliary words, not studied before, "on account of" - sababli, "due to " – -ga ko`ra, tufayli.

Words and word-combinations providing logical connections between separate parts of the text and providing the logic of an account.

E. g. to begin with – avvalambor;

Furthermore – bundan tashqari;

Summing up – qisqa qilib aytganda.

Differences in British English and American English:

company – corporation

programme – program

Texts of CoE official documents as well as documents of other international organizations (IO) belong to the official style of language. The aim of communication in the official style is to bind the addressee to a certain kind of behaviour. Therefore, these texts are artefacts with high degree of authority and binding force. They are intended to change behaviour of people and, therefore, to change the reality. The label of performatives may also be applied to these texts.

V. Kaliuzhna considers that IO documents considerably differ from other documents of the official style and claims that they belong to the language of IO documents – a substyle of the official style of language.³

Samples of official documents in English

³ Shikha Kendra, 2, Confectionary, Students Handbook and Practical Manual, Class XI Community Centre, PreetVihar, Delhi - 2014.

Mansfield and Co.
59 High Street
Swanage (=the address of the sender)
14 August, 2006 (=the date)

22 Fleet Street
London (= the address of the party addressed)

Dear Sir, (=salutation)

We beg to inform you that by order and for account of Mr. Jones of Manchester, we have taken the liberty of drawing upon you for \$45 at three months' date to the order of Mr. Sharp. We gladly take this opportunity of placing our services at your disposal, and shall be pleased if you frequently make use of them. (=body)

Truly yours,
Mansfield and Co. (=closing)
by Mary Smith

Official documents of Uzbek language also has its specific features. The famous uzbek linguist N. Mahmudov and others have published books named "Davlat tilida ish yuritish".

This book provides samples of Uzbek documents.

1. Official document on the servis area (Rasmiy (xizmat sohasidagi) ishonchnoma)

Ishonchnoma

Ishonchnoma

Kollejning
to'rtburchak
muhri

Jizzax pedagogika kolleji iqtisodiyot va tadbirkorlik bo'yicha direktor o'rinbosari Olimov Tohir Karimovichga "Dinamo" sport mollari do'konidan kollejga ajratilgan 10.000000 (o'n million) so'mlik sport jihozlarini olishga ishonch bildiradi.

Ishonchnoma 2008-yil 15-mayigacha amal qiladi.

Kollej direktori

(imzo)

S. Umarov

(muhri)

Ishonchnoma

"O'zbekiston" Mas'uliyati cheklangan jamiyat iqtisodchisi

Korxonaning
to'rtburchak
muhri

Karim Salimovich Olimovga Navoiy qurilish jihozlari korxonasi bilan 2005-yilning oxirgi choragiga qadar 100 mingta g'isht yetkazib berish to'g'risida shartnoma tuzish hamda mazkur topshiriq bilan bog'liq barcha ishlarni bajarishga vakolat beriladi.

Ishonchnoma 2007-yilning 10-mayigacha amal qiladi

Rais

(imzo)

A. Elmonov

(muhri)

Ishonchnoma

Men, Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti Iqtisodiyot fakultetining III kurs talabasi Saidahmad Isomiddinovich Lochinov hamqishlog'im Karim Omonovich Turg'unovga (pasport seriyasi ... №...) universitet kassasidan menga tegishli 2008-yil oktabr oyi stipendiyasini olish uchun ishonch bildiraman.

2008-yil 28-oktabr` (imzo) S.I. Lochinov

S.I.Lochinovning imzosini tasdiqlayman. Kadrlar bo'limi boshlig'i (imzo)

B.N. Yoqubov (muhr)

TILXAT

Tilxat - biror shaxsdan yoki muassasa (tashkilot, korxonalar, xo'jalik) dan pul, qimmatbaho buyumlar olinganligini tasdiqlovchi rasmiy yozma hujjat.

Tilxat bir nusxada tilxat beruvchining o'z husnixatida yoziladi va pulli, qimmatbaho hujjat sifatida saqlanadi.

Tilxat quyidagi zaruriy qismlar asosida yoziladi:

1. Hujjatning nomi (Tilxat).

2. Matn:

a) tilxat beruvchining lavozimi, familiyasi, ismi, ota ismi;

b) pul, hujjat, buyum yoki boshqa qimmatbaho narsani beruvchi shaxsning lavozimi, familiyasi, ismi va ota ismi (zarur bo'lganda muassasa nomi ko'rsatilishi mumkin);

v) olinayotgan qimmatbaho buyumning to'liq va aniq ro'yxati (pul miqdori va buyumlar soni avval raqam bilan, so'ng qavs ichida so'z bilan yoziladi);

g) olinayotgan buyumning texnikaviy holati (agar u mashina, qimmatbaho kompyuter, EHM kabilar bo'lsa)

3. Tilxat berilgan sana.

4. Tilxat muallifining imzosi.

Tilxatdagi yozuvlarni o'chirish yoki tuzatish mumkin emas, chunki bunday hujjat buzilgan, ya'ni qalbaki hisoblanadi.

Yirik miqdordagi pullarga beriladigan tilxat notarial idoralar tomonidan tasdiqlanadi va pul-buyumlarni sud orqali undirishga asos bo'ladi.

Olinadigan pul miqdori yoki buyumning bahosi va uning soni tilxatda raqamlar bilan ko'rsatiladi, qavs ichida esa so'zlar bilan qayd etilishi shart.

Tilxat

Men, O'zbek tili kafedrasini o'qituvchisi Abdumurod Zokirov, Falsafa fakul'teti talabalariga amaliy mashg'ulot o'tish uchun o'zbek tili o'quv xonasidan 10 (o'n)ta "Davlat tilida ish yuritish amaliyoti" o'quv qo'llanmasini oldim. Dars tugagach, keltirib topshiraman.

2008-yil 20-mart (imzo) A.Zokirov

1-mashq. Quyidagi berilgan matnni zaruriy qismlar asosida tartib bilan yozing. Nitijada tilxat namunasi hosil bo'lsin.

Muhammad Tarag'ay Ulug'bekning 600 yilligi munosabati bilan o'tkaziladigan anjuman oldidan... Tilxat, Men, Samarqand davlat universiteti Tarix fakul'tetining talabasi A'zamov Behzod, ... 1994.15.04. Kitoblarni anjuman tugagandan so'ng keltirib topshirish majburiyatini zimmamga olaman. (imzo) ... universitet kutubxonasidan ... B.A'zamov Ulug'bekning hayoti va faoliyatini yorituvchi burchak tashkil etish maqsadida... Ulug'bekning hayoti va faoliyatiga bog'liq 30 (o'ttiz) dona kitob oldim. (Ro'yxat ilova qilinadi).

2-mashq. Quyidagi tilxat matnida tushirib qoldirilgan qo'shimchalarni to'g'ri qo'yib, daftaringizga ko'chiring.

Men, Ishtixon tuman... "Yangiobod" fermer xo'jaligi rahbari Erkinov Muyassar, xo'jaligimiz hududida tashkil etilgan "Zafar" dehqon-fermer xo'jaligi rahbari Sodiqov Ahmad bilan hamkorlikda Samarqand viloyati "Tadbirkor" banki... 50.000.000 (ellik million) so'm kredit ol... Bir yil ichida mazkur miqdordagi pul... qo'shimcha 15% (o'n bez foiz) bilan qaytarib topshirish majburiyati... zimma... ol...

2007-yil 10-may (imzo) M.Erkinov

DALOLATNOMA

Dalolatnoma - biron bir xo'jalik, tashkilot, korxon va muassasa yoki ayrim shaxslar faoliyati bilan bog'liq bo'lgan voqea, hodisa, ish-harakatni yoxud mavjud holatni tasdiqlash, unga guvohlik berish maqsadida bir necha kishi tomonidan tuzilgan hujjat.

Dalolatnoma, asosan, pul mablag'lari, moddiy boyliklarga bog'liq holda tuziladi. Moliya-xo'jalik faoliyatida muayyan ishni qabul qilish, tekshirish yoki taftish o'tkazish, xo'jalik buyumlari va jihozlarini hisobdan o'tkazish yoki hisobdan chiqarish, baxtsiz hodisalar, tabiiy ofatlar natijalarini tekshirishda, qonunlar buzilishi va boshqa holatlarda dalolatnomalarga murojaat etiladi.

Dalolatnomalar voqea-hodisalarni haqqoniy aks ettirish maqsadida bir necha shaxslar (muassasa rahbarining buyrug'i bilan komissiyalar, doimiy komissiyalar) yoki maxsus vakolatli yakka shaxs tomonidan tuziladi.

Dalolatnoma farmoyish yoki buyruq berishda ma'muriyat uchun asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Dalolatnoma quyidagi zaruriy qismlar asosida tuziladi:

1. Bosh idora, muassasa va tarkibiy bo'linma nomi (zarur bo'lsa).
2. Hujjat nomi (Dalolatnoma). 3. Tuzilgan sanasi va joyi.
4. Tartib raqami va tasdiq belgisi.
5. Matn sarlavhasi.
6. Hujjatni tuzish uchun asos (muassasa rahbarining buyrug'i, yuqori idoraning qarori yoki ko'rsatmasi kabilar).
7. Komissiya tarkibi (raisi va a'zolari).
8. Ishtirok etuvchilar (guvohlar).
9. Dalolatnoma matni.
10. Ilovalar (har bir ilovaning necha betligi ko'rsatiladi).
11. Dalolatnoma tuzuvchilar va ishtirok etganlarning imzolari.

Dalolatnoma namunasi

Tasdiqlayman

Yangiobod fermer xo'jaligi raisi _____

S.A.Rahmatov 2008-yil 25-may

"Moybuloq" qishlog'i

Yangiobod fermer xo'jaligi bosh hisobchisining ishni topshirishi haqida

Dalolatnoma

Asos: fermer xo'jaligi raisining 2005-yil 17-maydagi 116-raqamli buyrug'i.

Fermer xo'jaligining sobiq bosh hisobchisi I.Rasulov va yangi tayinlangan bosh hisobchi S.Ikromovlar tomonidan, fermer xo'jaligi hisobxona xodimi R.Bozorov va ish yurituvchi R.S.Tojiyevlar ishtirokida tuzildi.

Fermer xo'jaligining bosh hisobchisi bo'lib ishlagan I.Rasulov ishni topshirdi, S.Ikromov qabul qilib oldi.

Qabul qilib olingan narsalar:

1. Fermer xo'jaligida ishlovchi barcha a'zolarining shaxsiy hujjatlari (ro'yxat ilova qilinadi).
2. Fermer xo'jaligi a'zolarining mehnat daftarchalari.
3. 2005-2008-yillar uchun 81 hujjat (ro'yxat ilova qilinadi).
4. Fermer xo'jaligining davlat gerbi aks ettirilgan muhr.

Dalolatnoma uch nusxada tuzildi:

1-nusxa - fermer xo'jaligi bosh hisobchisiga.

2-nusxa - fermer xo'jaligi hujjatlar yig'ma jildiga solib qo'yish uchun.

3-nusxa - ishni topshirgan xodimga.

Ishni topshirdim (imzo) I.Rasulov

Ishni qabul qilib oldim (imzo) S.Ikromov

Ishtirok etganlar: (imzo) R.Bozorov

(imzo) R.Tojiyev

Taking everything into consideration, we can conclude that in the official documents in English there are some informations about a document and peculiar features of the style of official documents, some aspects of documents a number of examples of standard documents, the translation problems of official documents, the types of factors of translation theory, some linguistic features which influence on the process, peculiar features of the style of official documents vocabulary level translation of official documents, the importance of the special terminology ,the lexicon of the standard documents, some information of international organizations according to the reality of

V.Kaliuzhna international organization documents characters classifications of international organization documents according V. Kaliuzhna .

Besides, those there are texts of building documents with the title resolution and recommendation texts of information documents and so on.

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